
**COMMUNICATION AS AN ADMINISTRATIVE PRACTICE OF
SCHOOL PRINCIPALS AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN
PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE,
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study examined how principals' administrative practice of communication predicts the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The Job Characteristics Model Theory of Hackman and Oldham (1976) was used to guide the study. One research question and a corresponding null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 254 school principals and 7388 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The sample was 739 teachers from the three Senatorial Districts, selected through the clustered sampling technique. Two research instruments tagged "Principals' Administrative Practice of Communication Questionnaire" (PAPCQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The questionnaires were administered and the data generated in this study were analyzed using Simple Linear Regression analysis. The research hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that principals' administrative practice of communication significantly predicts teachers' job performance in lesson preparation, lesson delivery, classroom management, use of instructional materials and students' assessment in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the finding of the study, it is recommended among other things that Principals of schools should be effective and efficient communicators. Instructions and directives should be unambiguously sent to teachers through effective means of communication as agreed upon by the members of the school system.

Keywords: Communication, Job Performance, Classroom Management, Instructional Materials

1 Introduction

Communication, according to Yalokwu (2002), is the effective transmission of common understanding among people through speech, writing, or other means. The author claims that communication does not occur unless a perfect understanding is achieved through the transmission of verbal or nonverbal symbols. Likewise, Communication, according to Eze and Ndukwu (2016), is a compelled effort by persons involved in the school system to express their personal sentiments, purposes, and information, as well as to appreciate the feelings, intentions, and knowledge of others. Egwuasi (2004) from another perspective considers effective communication as one based on face-to-face interactions, between people working to establish and maintain mutual trust and understanding. From the view of Obisi (2003), communication is generally understood as spoken or written words. But in reality, it is more than that. It is the sum total of directly or indirectly, unconsciously or consciously transmitted words, attitudes, feelings, actions, gestures, and tones. Even silence is an effective way of communication. Similar to this, Nwosu (2017) stressed that communication is a managerial tool frequently used to share information with members of staff, coordinate activities, reduce unnecessary managerial burdens and rules, and ultimately improve organizational performance. It is also a means by which staff is informed of various duties and how to perform it. Communication helps in coordinating the efforts of staff in school. Akinnubi, Gbadeyan, Fashiku and Kayode (2012) pointed out that communication is essential for understanding roles and assignments; planning and carrying out activities; coordinating approaches with students; providing information to teachers on students' progress and behaviours; and building a positive relationship with students, teachers and other staff. In the same vein, Ejeh and Okoro (2016) asserted that through communication, management can establish mutual understanding and exchange of ideas, information, experience and innovation for peaceful co-existence, conflict resolution, cumulative development, progress and well-being of the organizational structure. A problem or misunderstanding may arise if there is a breakdown in communication or the principal fails to provide timely information to members of staff. Iskandar, Ahmad, and Martua (2014) asserted that managers who are involved in the communication process need to possess both basic skills and abilities; otherwise, the information could be misunderstood.

According to Jay (2014), teachers' job performance is the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes. Bolarinwa (2016) observes that, the indicator of teachers' job performance is evaluated in the teachers' ability to make a deliberate effort to

enhance students' academic performance, possession and display of in-depth knowledge of subject matter, lesson presentation, effective classroom organization and control, and participation in the school curriculum activities. Other indicators of teachers' job performance according to the author include regularity and punctuality in the school, maintenance of good interpersonal relationship with subordinates and superiors, discipline, motivation, and counseling of students as well as compliance to teachers' professional codes of conducts among others. In other words, teachers' job performance is the degree to which teachers successfully accomplish their instructional responsibilities. A teacher can be said to have performed when the teacher plans his/her lessons according to standards, delivers lessons comprehensively, manages the classroom well, uses instructional materials to facilitate teaching, carries out formative and summative assessments regularly, keep records of students' progress, participates in sporting activities as well as all other functions of the school for the attainment of the set goals of the school.

Education is a vital tool for the development of man socially, economically, politically and otherwise for his well-being and opportunities for better living. It ensures the acquisition of knowledge and skills that enable people to increase their level of productivity and improve their quality of life. This increased productivity leads to new sources of earning which enhances the economic growth and the development of a country. The process of education begins and ends with communication because communication indisputably is as old as man and the smooth running of every system, organization, or establishment that leads to the attainment of the set objectives is only possible if there is effective communication.

The administration of the public secondary schools in Nigeria with emphasis on Akwa Ibom State is faced with a lot of problems like teachers' consistent cases of defaulting in lesson preparation, persistent lateness to school and classes, irregular and unauthorized movement from duty post, failure to mark and correct students' work, non-utilization of instructional materials, inability to convincingly explain difficult concepts to students and above all, poor classroom management skill amongst others. Embarrassingly too, students are no longer studious. They do not come early to school, most default in homework and some even engage in cultism. As a result, failure is recorded in both their internal and external examinations.

"Could the negative attitude of teachers toward the performance of their job, which is currently harming student performance, be as a result of the

administrators' administrative practice of communication in public secondary schools?" it is reasonable to inquire. This is an important question since teachers are the major drivers in the educational system, and their effective job performance determines the system's success or failure. It is against this background that the researcher decided to investigate how principals' administrative practice of communication predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In other words, what is the extent to which principals' administrative practice of communication predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

The study was designed to examine the extent to which principals' administrative practice of communication predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. this objective is driven from key questions like:

To what extent does principals' administrative practice of communication predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

The null hypothesis to be tested is stated thus;

The extent to which principals' administrative practice of communication predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

The scope of this study covered all the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria during the 2020/2021 academic year which ended in July 2021. The investigation centered on the principals' administrative practice of communication. Job performance of teachers was measured in terms of lesson preparation, lesson delivery, use of instructional materials, classroom management, and students' evaluation in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

2 Theoretical Framework.

2.1 The Job Characteristics Model Theory: Hackman and Oldham (1976)

The Job Characteristics Model Theory aims to specify conditions under which people are satisfied by their work and motivated to perform effectively. Hackman and Oldham (1976) identified five core characteristics, along with

three psychological states acting as a sort of ‘gateway’ to satisfaction. The five core characteristics are:

- i. Skill variety: As the name implies, this characteristic refers to the presence of different kinds of challenges at work.
- ii. Task identity: The degree to which a job calls for completion of discrete, ‘whole’ pieces of work.
- iii. Task significance: Whether the job has substantial impact on the lives/work of other people.
- iv. Autonomy: The degree of freedom or independence the job provides.
- v. Feedback: How clearly an individual is told about their performance.

The relevance of the theory to this study is that, for teachers to perform their duties as required, principals as school administrators should recognize the challenges that teachers encounter while performing their duties and also break the goals and objectives of the school system into short and long term achievable parts. Likewise, teachers deserve some level of independence while carrying out their responsibilities and should be provided feedback on their job performance from time to time as a way of motivating them.

2.2 Principals’ Administrative Practice of Communication and Teachers’ Job Performance

Communication to Osabiya (2015) probably is one of the most frequently cited sources of interpersonal conflict when it is poorly carried out. It is equally an important lifeline in every organization. Many of the problems that occur in organizations are the direct result of people failing to communicate. Lack of effective communication is a serious problem within an organization, and this can lead to confusion and can cause a good plan to fail. Communication is the source of information used by administrators in making decisions that affect the organization. Administrators depend on their communication skills to get the information required to make decisions and to transmit the results and intention of the decisions to other people.

Communication remains one of the most important aspect of human existence and very important in any organization (School inclusive) for the achievement of its set goals and objectives. Communication helps improve effective management of any organization this is because it improves the mutual understanding between the management and subordinates. Effective communication increases staff involvement and commitment in the organization for a better result. Yalokwu, (2002) sees communication as the effective transmission of common understanding among people through

speaking, writing or the other methods. The author asserts that unless there is a perfect understanding result from transmission of verbal or nonverbal symbols, otherwise communication has not taken place.

Egwuasi (2004) from another perspective sees effective communication as one based on face-to-face interactions, between people working to establish and maintain mutual trust and understanding. Think about it for a minute: what would a school be like without communication? My guess is that it would be very lonely not only could teams not co-ordinate their efforts and individuals seek feedback from and communicate their success to their supervisors, but also services would have tough time being delivered. If you could not communicate with co-workers, team members, customers and others with whom you routinely do business, you really would not have an organization at all. In Anderson (2012), when we fail to communicate we fail. What we communicate may not always be immediately applicable, but it can be a tool both for heading off potential problems and for laying the foundation of future growth. The role of effective communication skills is stressed as a primary mechanism for effective organizational improvement.

There are a range of verbal and non-verbal forms of communication. Verbal communication is a spoken communication. Information is exchanged from one person to another through spoken language. Non-verbal communication describes the process of conveying meaning in the form of non-word messages. For the supervisor to have a smooth career in the field of teaching, it is essential to group, practice and display high levels of communication skills. Effective communication acts as ladder to the principals for quick progression in their career.

Communication has four major functions within the organization (Osabiya, 2015). These include:

- i. Information: Communication facilitates decision making. It provides information that individuals and groups need to make decisions through the provision of data to identify and evaluate alternative choices.
- ii. Motivation: Communication fosters motivation by clarifying to employees what is to be done, how it will be done and what can be done. Communications and praises to employees also motivate and encourage commitment to organizational objectives.
- iii. Control: Communication acts to control member behaviour in various ways. Every organization has authority, hierarchies, Guidelines and Regulations that employees are required to follow For instance,

- employees know how to communicate their grievances, know which procedures to use to enjoy certain amenities or privileges and structures laid on how to process various requests.
- iv. Emotional Expression: Emotive uses of Communication allow for the expression of feelings and the satisfaction of social needs. Employees within their work groups Communicate among themselves to show their frustration or feelings of satisfaction which ultimately provides a release for their emotional expressions of feelings.

Communication can either be formal or informal. Communication is said to be formal, if the dissemination of information, messages and ideas are according to prescribed or fixed rules and customs. It is external rather than natural because it is notes a result of the intrinsic feelings of the actors but imposed on them by the organization (Obisi, 2003). Such

Communication is usually very rigid and follows definite pattern and it is official in nature. It may be oral or written, vertical or horizontal. They are usually bureaucratic in nature and the directives or instructions are to be carried out. Informal Communication is described as any interaction or relationship which exists in any organization which is not deliberate, rigid, or structured. Such interaction and relationship are as a result of natural feelings without any outside interference, constraint or premeditation (Obisi, 2003).

To improve communication in the school principals should:

- i. Regularly inform the ministry of the teachers' feelings, opinions, and ideas on important issues.
- ii. Involve teachers in decision making process.
- iii. Avoid blaming your subordinate when things go wrong.
- iv. Have a face to face discussion when dealing with a difficult situation.
- v. The principal should not let his opinion interfere with hearing what someone else is saying.
- vi. The supervisor should go out of his way to make teachers comfortable in approaching and speaking with him.

Nwoji (2006) found out that teachers' effectiveness in the performance of their duty is greatly influenced by the communication patterns of the school principal. He uses his communication skills to motivate, inform, suggest, warn, order, change behaviour, establish good relationship and make himself understood. There is no way a school can thrive without communication. Teachers' performance depends greatly on the supervisors' communication skills.

However, communication is very necessary in the organizational setting of secondary school system, but it does not provide solutions to all problems that border on school administration (Oleforo 2014). This was supported by Evans (2006) who revealed that leaders often fail to give feedback such as praise and redirection to those who trust in their leadership. She believes that feedback is a number one problem in interpersonal communication.

Okezue (2001), noted that communication gap resulted in misunderstand rumour, and counter-rumour, mistrust in schools administrations, lack of unity of purpose and suspicious among staff, which resulted in lack of commitment by the staff, lower standard of education, wastage in school management low morale, frustration among staff and indiscipline among staff and students.

In Communication, apart from the general distortions in the communication process, there are other barriers to effective Communication. These barriers could be examined from the four important levels of Communication, that is, Sender's levels, transmission/channels levels, receivers level and feedback level (Osabiya, 2015)

The sender of any particular message may not be particularly articulate either verbally or in writing, and will therefore fail to convey the information accurately. Where information is too scanty for the receiver to give adequate feedback or take a decision, it becomes a barrier. Many messages get lost because of the volume of information being passed to the receiver. When someone receives too many internal memoranda on relatively trivial issues, the important messages may get lost unless special attention is drawn to them in some way. When there is dislike between the sender and a receiver of a message, their emotional state will affect the way that message is perceived. Either the sender or the receiver may not listen or pay attention or may not be very objective to what is said on that topic. There is no doubt that communication itself is determined by our skills, knowledge and attitude and who we want to communicate with. Communication can only be effective when we adjust our knowledge and skills to the level of the receiver.

Physical Noise can easily distort communication flow. The more levels a message must go through to get to the bottom of the hierarchy, the more likely that a sizeable portion of the original information will be lost or substantially distorted. Selection of a poor channel of communication may also cause distortion of information.

Failure to understand the message by the receiver is a serious barrier. Where the receiver is threatened by the message or the receiver displays impatience for any reasons when receiving the message, communication may not be effective. When the receiver of the message is pre-occupied with other matters, the content of the message being received may not be fully appreciated. Where there is a negative attitude towards the receiver himself, the message and the sender, the communication may not likely be effective. Physical conditions or environmental factors may also prevent the receiver from understanding a message. Where the receiver does not understand certain "terms" used in the message, Communication becomes ineffective. When feedback not provided at all or is delayed, it may also affect effective Communication.

If an administrator desires to be a successful in the business of school administration, such school leader needs to be aware of the seven deadly sins of effective communication enumerated by Osabiya (2015). These include:

- i. Not realizing that the message may get a different response than you expect. People see the world differently, based on their experiences, values, attitudes, and perceptions. Expect to be misunderstood and adjust your message anticipating ways your ideas could be misinterpreted.
- ii. Impressing instead of expressing. First and foremost, the objective of communication is to transfer information, not exert power. Too often administrators are more concerned with sounding impressive and appearing knowledgeable than in making sure the ideas get across.
- iii. Choosing the wrong medium. It's easy to get in the habit of using the same medium over and over again. Administrators have choices: telephone, memos, letters, interviews, group meetings, electronic mail, etc. the one that will most effectively carry the message should be used.
- iv. Effective communication requires understanding by the recipient. Insist on feedback to be sure that the message received is the message sent.
- v. Studies show that as much as 78 percent of meaning is transmitted nonverbally through tone of voice, appearance, timing, and the like. Administrators should consider how the nonverbal messages might distort your intended message.
- vi. Administrators need to clarify the more important points in messages.
- vii. Communication is the essence of an administrator's job. It is not a morale booster. Good communication practices is not just a desirable quality; it is a requirement for effective administration.

In view of the barriers to communication identified and examined, it is expedient to consider what an administrator can do to minimize the problems

and attempt to overcome these barriers. The following suggestions/recommendations may be helpful in making Communication more effective.

- i. Administrators should be clear about the message to be conveyed and the reasons for the message.
- ii. The appropriate method of communication should be selected, having regard to content, timescale and target audience.
- iii. The message should be prepared in the appropriate format and language having particular regard to the nature and background of the people to be communicated.
- iv. Where possible, administrators should use more than one means of communication to reinforce the message and be prepared to repeat it if necessary.
- v. Administrators must maintain their integrity and credibility in the organization.
- vi. Administrators need to highlight the benefits of the message to the receiver.
- vii. Give examples, where appropriate to support the message.
- viii. Try to give factual information and careful explanation where required.
- ix. Structure any argument logically working up to the conclusions.
- x. Use any points that people will agree with to reinforce your statements.
- xi. Try to ensure that the message is interesting.
- xii. Avoid Communication overload and under load.
- xiii. Try to get and retain the receiver's attention.
- xiv. Use language that is at the experience level of the receiver.
- xv. Listen empathetically and make intelligent use of informal communication.

3 Methodology

3.1 Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of the 254 public secondary school principals and all the 7388 teachers of the public secondary schools in the three Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State.

3.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 739 teachers from the three senatorial districts (the thirty-three Local Government Area) which formed 10% of teachers of Akwa Ibom State. The sample was selected through the clustered sampling technique where the state was grouped into the three Senatorial Districts. 10% of the total number of teachers in each of the three Senatorial Districts was

further selected as sample through simple random sampling. Three students were also randomly selected to provide information on each teacher’s job performance from each of the three Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom.

3.3 Instrumentation

Two instruments named Principals’ Administrative Practice of Communication Questionnaire (PAPCQ) and Teachers’ Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were used to collect data from respondents (Teachers and students)

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analyzed using Simple Linear Regression analysis for research questions and null hypotheses. The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

4 Results

4.1 Answering the Research Question

Research Question: To what extent does principals’ administrative practice of communication predicts teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

To answer this research question, Simple Linear Regression analysis was employed, and the data obtained is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis for the extent to which principals’ communication predicts teachers’ job performance in public secondary school in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Variable	R	R-Squared	Extent of Prediction	Remark
Principals’ Communication(x)	0.698	0.488	48.7%	Moderate Extent
Teachers’ Job Performance(y)				

Source: Researcher Computation.

The entry in Table 1 reveals the R for the strength of the relationship and R² for the determination of the extent to which principals’ communication predicts

teachers' job performance. The R-squared value of .698 indicates the extent to which the prediction occurs. The calculated R^2 of .488 which is the coefficient of determinant indicates that only 48.7% variability in effectiveness is predicted or contributed by principals' communication. This implies that principals' communication to a moderate extent, predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.2 Testing the Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis: The extent to which principals' administrative practice of communication predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

Table 2: Simple linear regression analysis for the prediction between principals' communication and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Source of Variation	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F-cal	Sig.
Regression	74990.825	1	74990.825	699.321	.000 ^b
Residual	78816.797	735	107.234		
Total	153807.623	736			

Source: Researcher Computation

The entries in Table 2 revealed that the calculated F-value of 699.32 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 736 degree of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which claims that the extent to which principals' communication predicts teachers' job performance is not significant is rejected. The result reveals that principals' communication significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Finding

The result shows that there is significant prediction between principals' communication and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This result implies that principals' ability to disperse information to teachers on time and without any ambiguity, give good feedback to teachers, being polite in speech and a good listener contributes to a moderate extent to teachers' job performance.

Nwoji (2006) in support of this finding found out that teachers' effectiveness in the performance of their duty is greatly influenced by the communication patterns of the school principal. The principal uses his communication skills to motivate, inform, suggest, warn, order, change behaviour, establish good relationship and make himself understood. There is no way a school can thrive without communication. Teachers' performance depends greatly on the supervisors' communication skills. Evans (2006) revealed that leaders often fail to give feedback such as praise and redirection to those who trust in their leadership. The author believes that feedback is a number one problem in interpersonal communication. Likewise, Okezue (2001), noted that communication gap resulted in misunderstanding, rumour, and counter-rumour, mistrust in schools administrations, lack of unity of purpose and suspicious among staff, which resulted in lack of commitment by the staff, lower standard of education, wastage in school management low morale, frustration among staff and indiscipline among staff and students.

Abiodun-Oyebanji (2019) postulated that principals' application of different communication patterns in the administration of their schools' would lead to effectiveness of the school system. This then implies that, secondary school principals should be open to the usage of any of the communication patterns' suitable for their schools' situation, (most especially the face-to-face) since no communication pattern is independent of others; and this may facilitate the achievements of vision 2030. In support, Tyler (2016) uncovered five themes of communication in leadership which include a student-centered approach to decision-making, transparency of decision-making, shared decision-making with principal and teachers, the role of faculty trust, and principal preparation. Specific principal communication behaviors with teachers were implemented in motivating teachers toward earning high-performing status. These included frequent face-to-face and personal communications, minimal use of whole-school meetings, and weekly principal participation in grade level meetings. Nakpodia (2010) advised that in communication process principals should know that communication can never be over-emphasized in the daily running of the schools; as a result, principals should ensure that communication is effectively carried out to enhance discipline and to maintain law and order.

Osabiya (2015) opined that if an administrator desires to be a successful in the business of school administration, such school leader needs to be aware of the seven deadly sins of effective communication which are: i. Not realizing that the message may get a different response than you expect. ii. Impressing instead of expressing. iv. Effective communication requires understanding by

the recipient. v. Studies show that as much as 78 percent of meaning is transmitted nonverbally through tone of voice, appearance, timing, and the like.vi. Administrators need to clarify the more important points in messages. vii. Communication is the essence of an administrator’s job.

5 Recommendation

Based on the finding of the study, it is recommended among other things that Principals of schools should be effective and efficient communicators. Instructions and directives should be unambiguously sent to teachers through effective means of communication as agreed upon by the members of the school system.

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